

Pilot Guide

D7.2

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Deliverable D7.2 Pilot Guide

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DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
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CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

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Executive summary

As the EU moves towards sustainable energy, co-creation is the future of the energy service market. In the context of continuously increasing, highly distributed renewable generation, grid operators require more flexibility from the grid, this entails a shift in the balance of power, turning customers into a new generation of collaborators and putting them at the heart of the energy sector.

The SENDER project is financed by the European Commission, under the H2020 programme, which aims to **develop and test** the next generation of energy service applications for proactive Demand Response (DR), home automation convenience, and security mechanisms. In this line, by

engaging customers in a co-creation process, the project will shift DR from a reactive to a proactive approach.

To validate the elaborated use cases (energy solutions), which will be defined by a Co-creation Steering Group (WP2), three demonstration sites will be implemented along WP7. The three involved regions represent different cultures and have a different socioeconomic context, this way providing a wide spectrum to facilitate the replication of the solutions after the end of the project. Therefore, consumer engagement is one of the main issues to be addressed to develop effective demand response mechanisms, in this line the Sender project will (1) procure consumers engagement all along the project lifecycle and beyond by making them participants of the co-creation process and the further design and development of project solutions and (2) will develop guidelines (WP3) with consumer engagement strategies in order to help the different pilots reaching and retaining consumers into demand response mechanisms in the most efficient possible way.

This report presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that will be used to evaluate the efficiency of the Demand Response (DR) solutions implemented in SENDER demonstration. The document includes a complete list of KPIs and other relevant indicators, the methodology for the data collection and processing. The report also discusses the barriers, limitations and results expected from the demonstration, including a benchmark of literature and similar DR campaigns.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
BaaB	Building as a Battery	IML	Information Management Layer
CO2	Carbon Dioxide	KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DFFP	Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework	PV	Photovoltaic
DR	Demand Response	P2P	Peer-to-peer
DSO	Distribution System Operator	RES	Renewable Energy Sources
EMS	Energy Management System	SCI	Smart Control Interface
EV	Electric Vehicle	UC	Use Case
EVC	Electric Vehicle Charger	WHT	Water Heating Tank
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation & Air Conditioning	WP	Work Package

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
b	Baseline	i	Device
bal	Balance	j	Prosumer/Household
down	Downward flexibility	k	Demand Response event
el	Electricity	t	Time
flex	Flexibility	up	Upward flexibility
h	Hour		

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

This deliverable aims to define the right Key Performance Indicators (KPI) to evaluate the efficiency of a Demand Response (DR) system and the overall results of the pilots and its implementation, which will be analysed later in D7.6. The KPIs will serve to evaluate different aspects of the pilots, such as the efficiency of communication between stakeholders, the efficiency to flatten the demand of the participant households, the efficiency towards the sustainability of the DR program and the interest shown by end users, among other things. The KPIs aim to cover both technical and social aspects of the demonstration phase. In this sense, the selected KPIs measure or keep track of different aspects such as energy consumption, peak reduction, the demand variation and reshaping after DR is employed, price elasticity, rate of participation, comfort improvement or discomfort caused to users, and net economic benefits of the DR Programs. The selected KPIs will be used in T7.5 “Analysis of the results and recommendation” to assess the success of the project.

This deliverable provides a full list of KPI which will be monitored in the three pilots. In that sense, it will be also useful to detect the differences between the different pilots, and whether these may be related to climate conditions, differences in cultural behaviour, differences regarding the household equipment and devices, etc.

1.2. Relation with other tasks of the project

The pilots developed in WP7 are the core of SENDER project, hence they are related with most of the previous WPs. The primal objective of the pilot demonstration is to test and validate the system architecture defined in D3.1, as well as the specific modules developed for flexibility forecasting and provision. Another key aspect is to implement and validate the engagement strategies defined in D3.2, not only for the recruitment phase but also for the persistence of the users to be interested and their will to keep involved in the project. Moreover, the content of the contracts between aggregators (or equivalent actors) and SENDER users providing flexibility, defined in D3.3 but still under discussion, will impact substantially the course of WP7 and the selection of appropriate KPIs.

On the other hand, the pilots will serve to test in real cases the consumer patterns and the digital twin developed in WP5, as well as the other technical solutions for DR developed in WP6.

Furthermore, the results obtained in the pilots, which depend on the selected KPIs presented in this deliverable, will be used for the development of the business model and exploitation plan to a large-scale replicability, described in WP8.

2. Methodology

The chapter describes the process which will be followed throughout SENDER demonstration to obtain the data for KPIs presented in the deliverable, emphasising the role of each partner and the expected schedule of implementation. The first section describes which data will be available from pilots' households and other external sources, how this data will be collected and treated to calculate useful indicators. The data analysis will be implemented in two stages: a periodical reporting on KPIs during the execution of the pilots and a final evaluation of the SENDER demonstration.

2.1. Data collection and handling

The registration procedure of households enrolled in SENDER pilots will provide the first set of data which will be used for their characterization. The registration form will collect **sociodemographic information** of the households involved, such as the number of people living in the household, gender, age and range of income, together with a basic description of their dwelling, such as the type, size and number of floors. The registration form can be accessed in Annex 1.1.

These forms will be disseminated through events and workshops carried out by the pilot partners during the recruitment phase. It will be possible to fill the form by hand during a physical event or in digital format available on the project website. They will be available in the three pilot languages as well as in English.

The **technical information** of the household, needed to carry out the installation of components, will be done initially with an audit made by phone call and completed during the installation of SENDER components, by the installers themselves. The audit template developed by HPT will be included as an Annex in deliverable 7.3 "Deployment Report", which is due to M30 (March 2023).

A complete list of the **controllable and flexible devices** involved in SENDER demonstration will be drafted for each household. The list will collect technical specifications, such as the nominal power and efficiency of HVAC, electric boilers and EV charging points and the battery capacity of EV and storage systems, when it applies. The **flexibility potential** offered by each household device will be so calculated as the total electrical load that can be controlled during the demonstration.

The characterization data of each household will be stored in a specific register in the IML cloud database, managed by HPT. This register should be updated under f circumstances, such as:

- 1) the first installation of SENDER solution or the integration of new equipment;
- 2) the drop out of an enrolled participant;
- 3) the failure or disconnection of specific components.

The effect of these occurrences will have to be correctly detected and communicated to the responsible party, to promptly intervene and update the corresponding register. To guarantee the correct functioning of SENDER solutions, a protocol for fault detection and resolution must be drafted by the SENDER Consortium before the beginning of the demonstration.

During the demonstration phase, the monitoring devices installed to the enrolled households will provide detailed monitored data on the inhabitants use and consumption patterns, as well as keeping track of comfort conditions (temperature, humidity, light level, etc.). Figure 1 shows the system architecture defined in D3.1, illustrating the interaction between the components installed.

Figure 1: SENDER system architecture, as defined in deliverable 3.1

Table 1 shows all the available data required for the KPI calculation, which will be collected and processed by the Smart Box and the other modules integrated in SENDER architecture. The table specifies the data granularity and source: *monitored*, *obtained* (external), *forecasted* or *calculated*.

The table also specifies which SENDER component will provide the presented data, as well as the responsible partner, and for which Use Cases (UC) it will be used.

This information is obtained from the three software components integrated in SENDER solution: the *Electric Vehicle Charging Energy Management System (EV EMS)*, the *Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework for buildings (DFPF)* and the *Smart Control Interface for water heater tanks (SCI WHT)*. The components will evaluate the disposable flexibility of each device, which will be presented to the aggregator in the form of a flexibility forecast profile, or schedule, for each household with a timestep of 15 minutes. The functionalities of each component are described in detail in the deliverable 6.3 “Demand Response profiling and BaaB optimization”.

Each component will maintain a separate communication with the aggregators and will store the data on device activations independently. During the demonstration, the solution providers will have to calculate part of the indicators proposed in the deliverable at any 15-min timestep. They will also be responsible to provide ECO with access to their databases, to proceed with the analysis of results.

SENDER IML database will store all the information collected by the monitoring and sensing components, together with the data obtained from the DFPF. The frequency of data collection may vary according to the monitoring or sensing device involved, but only a reference 15-min timestep will be used for the analysis. Additional information on the monitoring or sensing solutions installed in pilot households can be accessed in deliverable 3.4 “Specification of supervision package”.

Table 1: List of input data collected during SENDER demonstration required for KPI calculations

SENDER component	Input data	Unit	Granularity	Source	Use Case	Partner	Description
Device Monitoring & Sensing	Energy monitoring from smart meters, clamps & plugs		event-driven	Monitored		HPT	Voltage, current, power and energy consumption of each device and total, PV generation
	Device status	Binary	event-driven	Monitored		HPT	Monitoring data from controllers & actuators regarding the device status and end-users' configuration
	HVAC setpoint	°C	event-driven	Monitored			
	HVAC mode	HEAT/COOL	event-driven	Monitored			
	HVAC fanspeed		event-driven	Monitored			
	Measures of multisensor located in building spaces			event-driven	Monitored		HPT
Building Flexibility Profiling Framework	Baseline & flexible thermal comfort boundaries	°C	15 min	Calculated	UC1	HPT	Trained comfort profile extracted for each building space, calculated using either maximum or flexible comfort boundaries
	Baseline power consumption profile of device & prosumer	W	15 min	Forecasted	UC1	HPT	Day-ahead forecast of each device and all devices of a single prosumer
	Flexibility (down/up) offered by device & by prosumer	W	15 min	Forecasted	UC1	HPT	Sum of flexibility profiles of each device and all devices of a single prosumer
Load & DER Forecasting Service	Measured & forecasted outdoor air temperature	°C	15 min - 1h	Obtained		CRS4	Acquired by weather web service for building location
	Forecasted Global solar radiation	W/m ²	15 min - 1h	Forecasted		CRS4	Estimated based on cloud coverage data acquired by weather web service
	Deterministic load forecast of prosumer	W	5 min	Forecasted	UC1, UC2, UC3	CRS4	
	Deterministic PV power forecast of prosumer	W	5 min	Forecasted	UC2	CRS4	
EV Charging EMS	Charging data per EVSE	W	15 min	Monitored	UC1, UC2, UC3	TRIALOG	Power setpoints and/or schedules for each EVSE of the charging station
	Monitoring data from charging station operator		15 min	Monitored	UC1, UC2, UC3	TRIALOG	EV charging profiles, EVSE status, meter values
Smart Control Interface for WHTs	Monitoring data from WHTs			Monitored	UC1, UC2, UC3	NXT	Power consumption, water level, set and monitored temperature
	Flexibility activation request from aggregator		event-driven	Obtained	UC1	HPT NXT TRIALOG	Flexibility schedule, proposed price and potential energy constraints
	Dynamic electricity tariff	€/kWh	1 hour	Obtained	UC1, UC2, UC3	ECO	Acquired by open data web service of national TSO at pilot site
	Dynamic emission factor	kg CO ₂ /kWh	1 hour	Obtained		ECO	

The compliance with GDPR is assured for the data handling, in accordance to the procedures defined in deliverable 4.1 “Data Management Plan”. Specifically, the monitoring and sensing data are collected in *Dataset 2* and *Dataset 3*, described in the subchapter “2.3 Types and formats of data generated/collected” of D4.1.

2.2. Periodical KPI assessment and pilot evaluation

To assess the implementation of SENDER pilots, a series of performance indicators will be presented periodically to participants and project partners and analysed for the continuous assessment of SENDER solution, the detection of deficiencies, trends, and areas of improvement.

Part of the KPIs calculated periodically will be made available to each enrolled household via the SENDER app. The users will be kept informed of the results obtained in terms of the amount of flexibility dispatched, the economic savings in their energy bills and the CO2 emissions savings obtained through SENDER demonstration. The solution providers will maintain a separate communication with the SENDER app, which will then present those KPIs separately according to the technical solutions responsible for the accomplishment (*EV EMS*, *DFPF* and *SCI WHT*).

The periodical results will be presented in the notification sections of the SENDER app. The notification of results is intended to maintain users engaged with the project and to provide a deeper understanding about their energy usage.

The relative changes from previous periods of analysis and from the historical average will be presented to SENDER consortium. The continuous follow-up of KPIs will help identify potential correlations and useful insights, which will be developed in-depth at the end of the demonstration.

At the end of the one-year long demonstration phase, the final evaluation of SENDER will be carried out, according to the KPIs presented in this deliverable (see section 3), which are designed to demonstrate the effectiveness of SENDER for each use case. The data collected during the whole year and stored in the database will point out which are the most successful actions in terms of impact, whether it is environmental, energy or monetary savings, and see if it applies in the same way for every pilot, or there are noticeable differences between them or between household types.

3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

This chapter presents the different Key Performance Indicators selected to evaluate the effectiveness of the SENDER solution according to the Use Cases that the project seeks to address, as well as the engagement strategies implemented.

3.1. Overview of selected KPIs

The indicators are categorized according to the **five Use Cases (UCs)** defined in Deliverable 2.4 “Use Cases Report”. Additional categories are the **participation in the SENDER demonstration**, which includes the set of flexible devices available, the **activation of flexible devices**, common to all UCs implementing demand-side flexibility (UC1, UC2 and UC3), and the **indicators of engagement**, expressing both the reach and satisfaction of SENDER demonstration.

No KPI was defined for the remote monitoring and control services (UC4), since this UC was designed only as a complement to the SENDER solutions which could enhance users’ experience.

In order, the different categories created to organize the sets of KPIs are:

- Participation in SENDER demonstration
- UC1. Explicit demand-response
- UC2. Maximize RES self-consumption
- UC3. Minimize energy bills
- UC5. Peer to peer trading
- Indicators of engagement

Table 2 collects all the KPIs defined for each category, while Table 3 contains a list of all auxiliary variables which will be used to calculate the KPIs or to supplement the data analysis. Both tables show the unit, scale (Household or Pilot) and frequency of measure of the presented indicators.

Table 2: List of KPIs for SENDER demonstration assessment

KPI	PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
0.1	Number of households enrolled in SENDER		X			
0.2	Flexibility potential available from controllable devices		X			
KPI	UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
1.1	Flexibility dispatched - Total and share of load					X
1.1.EV	Flexibility dispatched from EV (up/down)	X				
1.1.HVAC	Flexibility dispatched from HVAC (up/down)		X			
1.1.WHT	Flexibility dispatched from WHT (up/down)			X		
1.2	Load balance – Total and share of flexibility dispatched					X
1.3	Peak-to-Average load ratio – Forecasted and monitored					X
1.4	Profitability of explicit demand response for user					X
1.5	Emissions saved through flexibility dispatchment					X
1.6	Share of successful activations of flexible devices	X	X	X		X
1.7	Share of time in flexible comfort range		X			X

KPI	UC2. MAXIMIZE SELF-CONSUMPTION	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
2.1	Avoided surplus electricity production sold to grid					X
2.2	Increase in share of self-consumption with SENDER					X
2.3	Electricity bills savings from self-consumption					X
2.4	CO2 emissions savings from self-consumption					X
KPI	UC3. MINIMIZE ELECTRICITY BILLS	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
3.1	Electricity bills savings from price optimization					X
3.2	Price reduction of electricity purchased with SENDER					X
3.3	CO2 emissions savings from price optimization					X
KPI	UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
5.1	Average number of successful bids in P2P platform				X	
5.2	Increased share of PV production used onsite				X	
5.3	Increased profit/savings from P2P trading				X	
5.4	CO2 emissions saved from increased use of PV				X	
KPI	INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
6.1	Number of people reached/engaged/registered					X
6.1.TG	Nº or people engaged per target group					X
6.2	Perceived comfort/control/satisfaction					X
6.3	Share of users completing SENDER demonstration					X
6.4	Nº of users interested to keep using SENDER					X

Table 3: List of auxiliary variables calculated for SENDER demonstration

PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
Nº of households enrolled per target group		X			
Nº of controllable EVCs, HVAC, WHT, lights and other devices	X	X	X		
Nº of households with PV (with/without storage)		X			
UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
Nº of EV flexibility activation demands received from aggregator	X				
Nº of requests of building flexibility dispatchment received		X			
Nº of WHT flexibility requests			X		
Nº and average duration of DR events					X
Price of flexibility sold to aggregator					X
Revenue from flexibility dispatchments					X
Cost of demand-response activation					X
UC2. MAXIMIZE SELF-CONSUMPTION	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
EV charging schedule load adaptation to PV optimization	X				
Building flexibility adaptation to PV optimization		X			
WHT load adaptation to PV optimization			X		
UC3. MINIMIZE ENERGY BILLS	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
EV charging schedule load adaptation to price optimization	X				
Building flexibility adaptation to price optimization		X			
WHT load adaptation to price optimization			X		

UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
Number of users/prosumers registered in P2P platform				X	
Nominal capacity of PV plants registered in P2P platform				X	
Monetary volume traded in P2P platform				X	
Average electricity price of P2P transaction				X	
Total electricity traded in P2P platform				X	
INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	TRIALOG	HPT	NXT	NTNU	ECO
Nº of communications/events (online/physical)					X
Nº of social media interactions with users/multipliers					X
Reliance on quantitative/qualitative data analysis					X

3.2. Detailed description of KPIs

This chapter describes in detail the KPIs and indicators proposed in this deliverable to assess SENDER demonstration. Each subchapter describes a category of indicators, first presenting the scope and then describing the general calculation methodology. When necessary, a brief description of the specific calculation steps and the outputs adopted by each SENDER solution is presented, together with a reminder of the deliverables describing the technical solutions implemented.

Each indicator is presented in a resume table stating the unit of measure, the scale, the frequency and the partner responsible for its calculation or collection. The KPIs are assigned a numerical code to simplify their reporting during the analysis.

3.2.1. Participants in SENDER demonstration

The first batch of indicators resumes the characteristics of the households participating in the SENDER demonstration and the set of flexible devices available. These indicators will be used as a base to calculate relative KPIs during the data analysis following the demonstration. They will be collected during the recruitment phase, and ideally there should remain constant during the pilot, although some modifications might need to be done.

The main KPIs defined are the total **number of households (0.1)** prepared to dispatch flexibility at each pilot site and the available **flexibility potential (0.2)** per household, in total and separated according to which SENDER solution is offering it.

KPI	PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
0.1	Number of households enrolled in SENDER	HPT	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based
0.2	Flexibility potential available from controllable devices	HPT	[kW - %]	HH	Event-based

Additional variables such as the total number of people involved, considering the **gender** indicated for each household component, and the number of households belonging to a **target group** (households with children, elders, young people and vulnerable households) will be updated after any household register is created or modified. In the same way, the number of **controllable and flexible devices** available at each pilot site will be constantly updated during the recruitment phase, based on technical specifications collected.

The **flexibility potential** offered by each household device represents the theoretical maximum power load that can be controlled during the demonstration. The flexibility potential thus

corresponds to or the difference between the maximum and minimum operating load of each device, which is equal to the nominal power for those devices that can be turned off.

PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
Nº of households enrolled per target group	HPT	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based
Nº of controllable HVAC, lights and other devices	HPT	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based
Nº of controllable EV chargers	TRIALOG	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based
Nº of controllable water heater tanks	NXT	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based
Nº of households with PV (with/without storage)	HPT	[nº]	PILOT	Event-based

The indicators in this category will be collected during the recruitment phase, through the registration forms and the household audits. The indicators are expected to remain stable during the year of demonstration. Still, some occurrences might impact the actual participation, for example:

- 1) the late enrolment of participants to the pilot (in case of lower participation than expected);
- 2) the integration or purchase of new equipment to an enrolled participant;
- 3) the drop-out of an enrolled participant;
- 4) the variation in the composition of an enrolled household;
- 5) the failure or disconnection of specific components.

These indicators will help to categorize the households into different groups, and better digest the data coming from the rest of KPIs regarding the different UCs, as they might be relations with some socioeconomic aspects.

3.2.2. Explicit Demand Response (UC1)

The proposed indicators will analyse the implementation of explicit demand-response (UC1) for SENDER participants equipped with, at least, a controllable electric HVAC system, a controllable water heater tank (WHT) or an electric vehicle (EV) including a smart charger at home. According to D3.1, smart lighting and other smart appliances can be included in UC1, if needed.

The effect of explicit DR actions will be generally assessed as the **load shift** (ΔP_{DR}) of each flexible device controlled by SENDER. The load shift is calculated as the difference between the monitored power consumption (P) and the forecasted baseline power consumption (P_b) of the device.

$$\Delta P_{DR,i} = \text{Load shift of device } i = P_i - P_{b,i}$$

In the context of the SENDER demonstration, **explicit DR** is offered to aggregators in the form of flexibility forecasts having a 15-minutes timestep. The average loads during the 15-minutes step are then used for the following calculations.

An aggregator can send an **activation signal** asking to dispatch the flexibility available from certain households' devices. If the aggregator requests flexibility from a single household for two or more continuous timesteps (30 minutes or more), the period will be analysed as a single **DR event**.

Generally, an aggregator requests the flexibility simultaneously to a large number of households, since its objective is to aggregate loads big enough to be marketable as grid balancing services.

The **flexibility dispatched** by a device (ΔE_{flex}) is calculated as the integral of the load shift of the device over the duration of the DR event (Δt).

$$\Delta E_{flex,i,k} = \text{Flexibility dispatched by device } i \text{ in DR event } k = \int_{t=0}^{\Delta t_k} \Delta P_{DR,i} \cdot dt$$

$$\Delta E_{flex,j,k} = \text{Flexibility dispatched by prosumer } j \text{ in DR event } k = \sum_{i \in j} \Delta E_{flex,i,k}$$

We refer to **upward demand flexibility** when a DR action increases the load, meaning the monitored power consumption is higher than the forecasted power consumption ($\Delta E_{flex} > 0$). On the contrary, we refer to **downward demand flexibility** when a DR action reduces the load, meaning the monitored power consumption is lower than the forecast power consumption ($\Delta E_{flex} < 0$).

Upward flexibility is expected when grid requires to increase its total load, which is foreseen to be below the grid capacity (*valleys*). In this case, a flexible load can be rescheduled to cover for the underconsumption (*valley filling*) or increased to absorb the excess of renewable production (*load building*). Downward flexibility is expected when the grid requires to reduce its total load, which is foreseen to be above the grid capacity (*peaks*). A flexible load can thus be reduced (*peak clipping*) or rescheduled away from the period of overconsumption (*load shifting*).

It should be noted that, in downward flexibility conditions, the literature usually refers to **peak load reduction** instead of *load shift*.

A DR event can be composed by both upward and downward demand flexibility actions. An example is the Building as a Battery (BaaB) solution, which (in the heating season) is composed of a pre-heating above the temperature setpoint (upward), followed by a heating load reduction to a relaxed comfort temperature threshold (downward).

Figure 2: Graphical representation of explicit demand response¹

¹ Image based on (Dyson et al., 2015)

Figure 3: Representation of upward and downward flexibility action typologies²

The **number of activations** of flexible devices will be considered separately for each component offered by SENDER: 1) the *Electric Vehicle Charging Energy Management System*, 2) the *Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework for buildings* and 3) the *Smart Control Interface for water heater tanks*.

This way the aggregators will be able to visualize separately the flexibility offered by 1) EVs, 2) HVAC and other building devices and 3) smart WHTs. The three components will maintain a separate communication with the aggregators, which will be able to select whether to activate one or more of the flexibility forecasts presented.

Each time a DR activation occurs after a request from an aggregator, the responsible partners will store the information on which devices participated, the baseline load, the total flexibility dispatched and the ID of the aggregator which requested the flexibility. The registers will have to explicitly specify for which UC the devices were activated, in this case UC1.

As described in deliverable 6.3, the EVC EMS tool calculates the flexibility potential of the EV, adds it to the aggregated flexibility potential of the whole charging station and sends it to the aggregator, which in return can send a flexibility activation demand. Upon reception, the EVC EMS runs its embedded algorithm to define the new charging schedules for the whole fleet, taking into account the flexibility demand. Once calculated, the tool sends those new charging data to the EVSEs. Those steps are repeated until the disconnection of the EV.

TRIALOG will collect the registers of all the offers sent to the aggregators (*OfferID*). Only those resulting in a flexibility activation demand will be used for the analysis (*OfferStatus == ACTIVE*). The output files are a JSON messages, which include the identification of the aggregator involved (*flexManagerId*). Since each offer refers to a 15-min period, consecutive activation demands will be analysed as part of a single DR event.

² Image based on (DG Ener, 2016)

UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
Nº of EV flexibility activation demands received from aggregator	TRIALOG	[nº]	HH	Periodical
Nº of requests of building flexibility dispatchment received	HPT	[nº]	HH	Periodical
Nº of WHT flexibility requests	NXT	[nº]	HH	Periodical
Nº and average duration of DR events	ECO	[nº - min]	HH	Periodical

ECO will be responsible to collect the information of technical partners and calculate summary indicators. Each period of analysis will thus account for the total **number of DR events** occurred per household and their **average duration**.

Similarly, the **flexibility dispatched** by each solution following a flexibility activation demand will be collected by the responsible technical partners and provided to ECO for the analysis.

ECO will calculate periodically the **total flexibility dispatched (1.1)** by a single household over the period of analysis, both in absolute terms (kWh) and as a share of the household's baseline electrical load, as forecasted by SENDER. The value will also be presented separately in terms of upward and downward flexibility dispatched. The maximum and the average flexibility dispatched in a single DR events will be calculated to assess the topmost contribution that a single household and a cluster of households can provide to the grid in case of request.

Taken together and aggregated at pilot level, these indicators will allow to extrapolate the flexibility potential of the SENDER solutions if implemented on national markets.

Finally, the **load balance (1.2)** of a prosumer over a certain period is calculated to distinguish the effect of load shifting (for which the upward flexibility is balanced by downward flexibility) from that of peak reduction or load building (which generates energy savings or extra consumption).

Finally, the **Peak-to-Average load ratio (1.3)** is used to express the flatness of an household's power consumption curve and is used to quantify the peak shaving obtained with DR.

KPI	UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
1.1	Flexibility dispatched – Total and share of load	ECO	[kWh - %]	HH	Periodical
1.1.EV	Flexibility dispatched from EV (up/down)	TRIALOG	[kWh]	HH	Event-based
1.1.HVAC	Flexibility dispatched from HVAC (up/down)	HPT	[kWh]	HH	Event-based
1.1.WHT	Flexibility dispatched from WHT (up/down)	NXT	[kWh]	HH	Event-based
1.2	Load balance – Total and share of flexibility dispatched	ECO	[kWh - %]	HH	Periodical
1.3	Peak-to-Average load ratio – Forecasted and monitored	ECO	[%]	HH	Periodical

Generally speaking, the total amount of flexibility dispatched by a prosumer is calculated as the sum of the upward ($\Delta E_{flex,up,j}$) and the module of downward flexibility ($\Delta E_{flex,down,j}$) dispatched by the prosumer j over the period of analysis. This value expresses the **deviation of the monitored load profile from the forecasted baseline** as a consequence of SENDER solution.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{flex,j} &= \text{Flexibility dispatched by prosumer } j = \Delta E_{flex,up,j} + |\Delta E_{flex,down,j}| \\ &= \sum_{k \in K_{up}} \Delta E_{flex,j,k} + \sum_{k \in K_{down}} |\Delta E_{flex,j,k}| \end{aligned}$$

Where K_{up} and K_{down} are the amounts of upward and downward flexibility events happened in the period of analysis.

The load balance of prosumer j is calculated as the sum of the upward and the downward flexibility dispatched by the prosumer over the period of analysis. This value expresses the ***difference in net electricity consumption from the forecasted baseline*** because of SENDER solution.

$$\Delta E_{balance,j} = \text{Load balance of prosumer } j = \Delta E_{flex,up,j} + \Delta E_{flex,down,j} = \sum_{k \in K} \Delta E_{flex,j,k}$$

The ratio between the load balance and the total flexibility dispatched over the same period helps distinguish the effect of load variation (reduction or increase) from that of load shifting. The indicator ranges between -1 (only downward flexibility) to 1 (only upward flexibility), with negative values representing an overall reduction in consumption (or energy savings due to DR) and positive values an increase (or energy costs of DR).

$$\text{Energy reduction or increase over DR} = \frac{\Delta E_{balance,j}}{\Delta E_{flex,j}} = \frac{\Delta E_{flex,up,j} + \Delta E_{flex,down,j}}{\Delta E_{flex,up,j} + |\Delta E_{flex,down,j}|}$$

The Peak-to-Average load ratio is calculated as a ratio between the maximum and average power load of a prosumer during the period of analysis. The indicator is expressed as a percentage always higher than 100%, which represents a completely flat curve. The Peak-to-Average ratio gain relevance when calculated on a daily basis, since it allows to easily compare different periods.

$$\text{Peak to Average load ratio of prosumer } j = \frac{\max_{t \in \Delta t}(P_j)}{\left(\frac{\int_{t=0}^{\Delta t} P_j \cdot dt}{\Delta t} \right)}$$

These indicators will be calculated by comparing the total power consumption of a prosumer, as collected by smart meters or smart clamps, with the total baseline power consumption profile for the prosumer, as forecasted by the *Load and DER Forecasting Service*. Both values are collected in SENDER IML database managed by HPT.

At the same time, the flexibility dispatched by each of SENDER solutions will be calculated separately by the responsible partners at every 15-minutes timestep. The aggregated value of the data provided by partners will be compared with the reference calculation, to ensure there is no discrepancy within the methodologies applied for the different solutions.

As described in deliverable 6.3, the flexibility extracted from EVs is the difference between the energy received at normal operation (maximal power capacity charging) and the energy that could be received during a period of time without endangering the satisfaction of EV driver's need (EV charged at departure time).

The flexibility offers sent by TRIALOG at any time frame (*OfferID*) collect the charging load profile (*min*, *max* and *default*) and the status of the offer (*WAITING_ACCEPTATION*, *ACTIVE*, *CANCELLED* and *EXPIRED*). The *default* value corresponds to the baseline, whereas the *min* and *max* values are absolute flexibility margins for each time frame.

Deliverable 6.3 describes how the day ahead baseline (*mean*) and flexibility forecasts (upward as *meanUp* and downward as *meanDown*) of building loads will be provided to aggregators using a Rest

API interface. The flexibility can be presented in absolute values, as calculated (*AbsoluteP*) or as a difference between the baseline and the flexibility estimations (*deltaP*).

Two KPIs will assess the economic and environmental benefits of SENDER UC1, in terms of **profitability of explicit DR (1.4)** and **emissions savings (1.5)** generated by flexibility dispatchment.

KPI	UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
1.4	Profitability of explicit demand response for user	ECO	[€]	HH	Periodical
1.5	Emissions saved through flexibility dispatchment	ECO	[kg CO2]	HH	Periodical

The profitability of DR is calculated by comparing the **revenues from flexibility dispatchment** with the **cost of activation** of flexible devices during a DR event. The revenues are calculated using the **price of flexibility** sold to aggregators, collected separately by each technical solution. On the other hand, the calculation of costs is based on the dynamic tariff schedule obtained by the national TSO³ or the market operator⁴ of each pilot site.

ECO will monitor the evolution of the economic indicators during the demonstration, to gain an overview of the flexibility market active in the pilot countries.

UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
Price of flexibility sold to aggregator	TRIALOG/HPT/NXT	[n°]	HH	Event-based
Revenue from flexibility dispatchment	ECO	[n°]	HH	Periodical
Cost of demand-response activation	ECO	[n°]	HH	Periodical

The revenue obtained from the flexibility dispatched to the aggregator is provided in the form of an incentive, the profitability is then calculated as the difference between the amount of the incentive provided (R_{flex}) and the total cost of DR activation (C_{DR}) over the period of analysis.

$$R_{flex,j,k} = \text{Revenue of prosumer } j \text{ from DR event } k = \Delta E_{flex,j,k} \cdot p_{flex,k}$$

$$C_{DR,j,k} = \text{Cost of DR event } k \text{ for prosumer } j = \Delta E_{bal,j,k} \cdot p_{el,j,k}$$

$$Pr_{DR,j} = \text{Profitability of explicit DR for prosumer } j = \sum_{k \in K} (R_{flex,j,k} - C_{DR,j,k})$$

The price or revenue of flexibility dispatchment will be defined according to the contracts signed between end-users and the party acting as an aggregator. At this point of the project, the discussions with potential partners are still ongoing, making it impossible to define the way the bidding process will be structured. Additional information on what information will be included in the bilateral contracts is available in D3.3 “Agreements for contracts DSOs / Consumers”.

In case a pilot cannot establish an agreement with an aggregator for its participation in the demonstration (as is the case of Spain), the potential revenue from explicit DR will be calculated as if the pilot was participating in a reference aggregator market.

³ Finnish pilot: <https://www.fingrid.fi/en/electricity-market/datahub/>

⁴ Spanish pilot: <https://www.omie.es/es/market-results/daily/average-final-prices/average-hourly-price>

In that case, since no revenue will be available to compensate the final user, it will be critical to maintain the cost of DR activation close to zero or, if possible, negative. The SENDER consortium has allocated budget in form of incentives to cover for eventual extra-costs that could be experienced by pilots' households.

The CO2 emissions saved in a DR event are calculated by multiplying the energy balance by the emission factor notified during the event ($EF_{el,k}$) for the pilot location. If just fixed emissions factor were available, the indicator could only reflect the savings of DR actions resulting in a load reduction.

$$\Delta CO2_{DR,j} = CO2 \text{ emissions saved by prosumer } j \text{ with DR} = \sum_{k \in K} (\Delta E_{bal,j,k} \cdot EF_{el,k})$$

Considering the time-dependency of DR actions, the use of dynamic emission factors will be needed to estimate the CO2 emissions savings triggered by SENDER UC1. The dynamic emission factors of the electricity production should be obtained from the TSO of each pilot site⁵⁶.

KPI	PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
1.6	Share of successful activations of flexible devices	ECO	[%]	HH	Periodical
1.7	Share of time in flexible comfort range	HPT/ECO	[%]	HH	Periodical

Finally, the overall efficacy of the activations will be assessed for each solution in terms of their **success rate (1.6)**, or the share of successful activations of flexible devices. This indicator will account either for the technical problems which might occur and for the overrides done by the final users by changing a setpoint or forcing a disconnection. The overrides are expected to be mostly unintentional, provoked by a sense of discomfort or an unexpected necessity (e.g. using the car).

These overrides are all the control actions made by users which disturb SENDER implementation, including those made through the SENDER app. At each control action a request is sent from the app to the Smart Box gateway asking to reset a parameter of a specific device. The SENDER IML will store data logs for each control action made by the users. However, the IML will not distinguish whether the control was made manually or through the app. An override is thus identified as any control action made by the user identified within a 15-min period of device activation, delimited by two control actions requested by SENDER.

The KPI will thus assess indirectly whether the remote monitoring and control (UC4) is compatible with the rest of SENDER solutions, based on full automation. Finally, if possible, the overrides will be categorized based on which device was controlled by users.

Flexibility aggregators and DSOs would be especially interested in knowing the probability of success to activate a DR event, because of the high atomization of the flexibility market offered by the residential sector.

The **share of time** spent by a household **in flexible comfort range (1.7)**, as required by the *Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework* module, will be also accounted to ensure SENDER's UC1 is not affecting users' comfort. This indicator will be compared with the answers given by users to a periodic qualitative questionnaire on their experience in the demonstration (See chapter 3.2.7).

⁵ Spanish pilot: <https://demanda.ree.es/visiona/peninsula/nacional/total>

⁶ Finnish pilot: <https://www.fingrid.fi/en/electricity-market-information/real-time-co2-emissions-estimate/>

3.2.3. Maximize RES self-consumption (UC2)

The proposed indicators will analyse the effects of the optimization algorithm designed to maximize self-consumption (UC2) of SENDER participants equipped with a PV plant and, at least, an EV charging point or a controllable WHT.

The UC2 optimization will be implemented separately by the *Electric Vehicle Charging Energy Management System* and the *Smart Control Interface for water heater tanks*. Based on the day-ahead PV production schedule forecasted at pilot level, both solution providers will adapt the operation of the devices under their control prioritizing the periods of PV production.

Specifically, based on the PV production data stored in its internal database, the initial configuration of the tool and the characteristics of the plugged EV, the EVC EMS defines the default charging schedule and sends the charging data (power setpoints) to the EV Supply Equipment.

At every timestep the responsible partners will store the information on which devices' schedule were adapted in that time frame, the corresponding baseline load and the total load flexibility triggered by the optimization.

In principle, the *Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework for buildings* will not participate in UC2. However, the contribution of HVAC and other building devices to UC2 is kept as an option for specific pilot sites, in case a scarcity of EVs and controllable WHTs is detected during the recruitment phase.

UC2. MAXIMIZE SELF-CONSUMPTION	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
EV charging schedule load adaptation to PV optimization	TRIALOG	[kWh]	HH	Periodical
Building flexibility adaptation to PV optimization	HPT	[kWh]	HH	Periodical
WHT load adaptation to PV optimization	NXT	[kWh]	HH	Periodical

The KPIs used to analyse the results of PV optimization will be the **avoided PV surplus sold to grid (2.1)** and the increase in the **share of self-consumption (2.2)**.

KPI	UC2. MAXIMIZE SELF-CONSUMPTION	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
2.1	Avoided surplus electricity production sold to grid	ECO	[kWh]	HH	Periodical
2.2	Increase in share of self-consumption with SENDER	ECO	[%]	HH	Periodical

The avoided surplus ($\Delta E_{surplus}$) is calculated as the difference between the monitored surplus of electricity ($E_{surplus}$) and the surplus forecasted under baseline conditions ($E_{surplus,b}$). Under normal circumstances, the value should correspond to the load flexibility triggered by the optimization, registered by solution providers, and should always be a positive value.

$$\Delta E_{surplus} = \text{Avoided surplus sold to grid} = E_{surplus,b} - E_{surplus} = \Delta E_{flex,j}$$

The self-consumption is calculated as the share of the electricity produced by the PV (E_{PV}) which is consumed directly by the household or stored in the battery. The monitored self-consumption of households implementing SENDER optimization is compared with the baseline self-consumption, calculated as if the household had not participated in the demonstration.

$$\%E_{UC2} = \text{Share of self consumption} = \frac{E_{PV} - E_{surplus}}{E_{PV}}$$

These indicators will be calculated by comparing the direct self-consumption from the PV-battery system of a prosumer, as collected by the smart clamps, and the electrical load supplied by the grid, as collected by smart meters, with the respective baseline values forecasted by the *Load and DER Forecasting Service*. These values are collected in SENDER IML database managed by HPT.

At the same time, the load adaptation profile will be provided by the responsible partners of each SENDER solution at every 15-minutes timestep. The aggregated value of the data provided by partners will be compared with the reference calculation, to ensure there is no discrepancy within the methodologies applied for the different solutions.

The KPIs used to assess the economic and environmental benefits of UC2 are the **electricity bills savings (2.3)** and the **CO2 emissions savings (2.4)** due to the increased share of self-consumption.

KPI	UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
2.3	Electricity bills savings from self-consumption	ECO	[€]	HH	Periodical
2.4	CO2 emissions savings from self-consumption	ECO	[kg CO2]	HH	Periodical

The electricity bill savings are estimated on an hourly basis as the difference between the price of purchase of electricity (p_{el}) and the sale price paid from the supplier for the surplus electricity ($p_{surplus}$), multiplied by the avoided surplus sold to the grid. To guarantee comparability, reference prices indexed to the local electricity market will be used for all households in the same location.

$$\Delta C_{el,UC2} = \text{Electricity bill savings} = \sum_h \Delta E_{flex,h} \cdot (p_{el,h} - p_{surplus})$$

The CO2 emissions savings due to the PV optimization are calculated hourly by multiplying the avoided surplus of electricity sold to the grid by the dynamic emission factor of the national electricity mix at each pilot location ($EF_{el,h}$). Where dynamic factors are not available (as for Austria), emission factors of the national electricity mix referring to 2021 will be used⁷.

$$\Delta CO2_{UC2} = \text{CO2 emissions savings} = \sum_h (\Delta E_{flex,h} \cdot EF_{el,h})$$

3.2.4. Minimize energy bills (UC3)

The proposed indicators will analyse the effects of the optimization algorithm designed to minimize energy expenditures (UC3) of SENDER participants equipped with, at least, an EV charging point or a controllable WHT.

The UC3 optimization will be implemented separately by the *Electric Vehicle Charging Energy Management System* and the *Smart Control Interface for water heater tanks*. Based on the day-ahead electricity market tariffs forecasted at pilot level, both solution providers will adapt the operation of the devices under their control prioritizing the periods of low price.

⁷ https://www.carbonfootprint.com/docs/2022_03_emissions_factors_sources_for_2021_electricity_v11.pdf

Specifically, based on the data stored in its internal database, the initial configuration of the tool and the characteristics of the plugged EV, the EVC EMS defines the default charging schedule and sends the charging data (power setpoints) to the EV Supply Equipment.

At every timestep the responsible partners will store the information on which devices' schedule were adapted in that time frame, the corresponding baseline load and the total load flexibility triggered by the optimization.

In principle, the *Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework for buildings* will not participate in UC3. However, the contribution of HVAC and other building devices to UC3 is kept as an option for specific pilot sites, in case a scarcity of EVs and controllable WHTs is detected during the recruitment phase, especially if a few of the households engaged own a PV system.

UC3. MINIMIZE ELECTRICITY BILLS	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
EV charging schedule load adaptation to price optimization	TRIALOG	[kWh]	HH	Periodical
Building flexibility adaptation to price optimization	HPT	[kWh]	HH	Periodical
WHT load adaptation to price optimization	NXT	[kWh]	HH	Periodical

The KPIs chose to assess the price-based optimization are primarily economic, in terms of **electricity bills savings (3.1)** and of **price reduction of electricity purchased (3.2)**. Also, where if dynamic emission factors are available, the environmental benefits of UC3 will be assessed in terms of **CO2 emissions savings (3.3)** generated by the optimization.

KPI	UC3. MINIMIZE ELECTRICITY BILLS	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
3.1	Electricity bills savings from price optimization	ECO	[€]	HH	Periodical
3.2	Price reduction of electricity purchased with SENDER	ECO	[€/kWh]	HH	Periodical
3.3	CO2 emissions savings from price optimization	ECO	[kg CO2]	HH	Periodical

The electricity bills savings are calculated on a periodical basis by multiplying the hourly electricity tariff ($p_{el,h}$) by the difference between the monitored electricity consumption (E) and the forecasted baseline consumption (E_b). The calculation will use reference prices indexed to the local electricity market for all households in the same location.

$$\Delta C_{el,UC3} = \text{Electricity bill savings} = \sum_h \Delta E_{flex,h} \cdot p_{el,h}$$

The average price of electricity purchased from the retailer ($p_{el,UC3}$) is calculated as a weighted average of the hourly electricity tariff over the monitored electrical load consumption of the household. The calculation is repeated using the forecasted baseline load to estimate the baseline price of electricity purchased ($p_{el,b}$) in case the SENDER solution was not implemented.

$$p_{el,UC3} = \text{Average electricity price of purchase} = \frac{\sum_h (E_h \cdot p_{el,h})}{\sum_h E_h}$$

As for UC2, the CO2 emissions savings due to the price optimization are calculated hourly by multiplying the the load flexibility triggered by the optimization by the dynamic emission factor of the national electricity mix at each pilot location. Where just fixed emissions factor are available, the indicator will not be calculated since it would lose any meaning.

These indicators will be calculated by comparing the total power consumption of a prosumer, as collected by smart meters or smart clamps, with the total baseline power consumption profile for the prosumer, as forecasted by the *Load and DER Forecasting Service*. Both values are collected in SENDER IML database managed by HPT.

At the same time, the load adaptation profile will be provided by the responsible partners of each SENDER solution at every 15-minutes timestep. The aggregated value of the data provided by partners will be compared with the reference calculation, to ensure there is no discrepancy within the methodologies applied for the different solutions.

3.2.5. Peer-to-peer trading (UC5)

The proposed indicators will analyse the effects of the peer-to-peer (P2P) trading platform designed to exchange the surplus of production of PV owners with their neighbourhoods (UC5) participating in SENDER.

The participation to UC5 will be expressed in terms of the **number of prosumers and users** and the total **nominal capacity** of the PV plants registered in the P2P platform.

UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
Number of users/prosumers registered in P2P platform	NTNU	[n°]	PILOT	Event-based
Nominal capacity of PV plants registered in P2P platform	NTNU	[kW]	PILOT	Event-based

The P2P platform operates by automatically launching bids to sell the excess PV production of prosumers based on the day-ahead market prices. The bids are randomly matched with offers of other users and so, any time a prosumer's bid satisfies another user's offer, the electricity is traded. The P2P trading will increase the share of PV production which is consumed onsite, either by the prosumer or by other users of the P2P platform. To quantify the increase in self-consumption, as for UC2, the PV production surplus sold to grid is compared with the surplus forecasted under baseline conditions (without SENDER). The main KPIs used to evaluate UC5 are, then, the average **number of successful bids (5.1)** closed within the P2P platform and the **increased share of PV production (5.2)** used onsite by P2P participants.

The increase of onsite PV consumption is associated with two other KPIs, accounting for the economical and environmental benefits of P2P trading: the **increased profits or bill savings (5.3)** obtained by P2P participants and the **CO2 emissions savings (5.4)** from the reduction of grid electricity usage. Once again, where possible, the CO2 emissions savings due to P2P trading will be calculated hourly using dynamic emission factor.

KPI	UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
5.1	Average number of successful bids in P2P platform	NTNU	[n°/d]	PILOT	Periodical
5.2	Increased share of PV production used onsite	NTNU	[%]	PILOT	Periodical
5.3	Increased profit/savings from P2P trading	NTNU	[€]	HH	Periodical
5.4	CO2 emissions saved from increased use of PV	NTNU	[kg CO2]	PILOT	Periodical

On the economic side, additional variables such as the total **monetary volume** and the average **transaction price** for the electricity traded in the P2P platform will be calculated. Similarly, the total volume of **electricity traded** within the P2P platform will be taken into account.

UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
Monetary volume traded in P2P platform	NTNU	[€]	PILOT	Periodical
Average electricity price of P2P transaction	NTNU	[€/kWh]	HH	Periodical
Total electricity traded in P2P platform	NTNU	[kWh]	HH	Periodical

3.2.6. Indicators of engagement

The proposed indicators will analyse the efficacy of the engagement strategies implemented in SENDER throughout different phases of the pilot demonstration: reaching the households willing to participate to the demonstration (*engagement*), collecting feedback on the SENDER experience during the demonstration (*response*) and assessing the will to keep using the SENDER solution after the demonstration ends (*persistence*).

KPI	INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
6.1	Number of people reached/engaged/registered	ECO	[n°]	PILOT	Demo start
6.1.TG	N° or people engaged per target group	ECO	[n°]	PILOT	Demo start

The first KPIs assess the number of **people reached, engaged, and registered (6.1)** (accounting for **gender, age** and belonging to a **target group**) through **communication** and physical **events**.

Additionally, the communication campaigns will be assessed in terms of interaction with potential users and multipliers, by analysing the statistics of **social media** profiles. Also, the reliance of the social make-up of pilots on **quantitative** and **qualitative data analysis** will be monitored.

INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
N° of communications/events (online/physical)	ECO	[n°]	PILOT	Demo start
N° of social media interactions with users/multipliers	ECO	[n°]	PILOT	Demo start
Reliance on quantitative/qualitative data analysis	ECO	[%]	PILOT	Demo start

Some qualitative indicators will be collected from participants throughout the demonstration to evaluate their satisfaction with SENDER solution. The users will be asked periodically to rank their **perceived level of comfort**, sense of **control** over devices and general **satisfaction (6.2)** using a 1-5 range. To complement the analysis, in-depth ad-hoc questionnaires will be filled during the feedback sessions organized throughout the demonstration.

The long-term engagement, or persistence, of SENDER participants will be assessed after the end of the demonstration by accounting the number of **users completing the demonstration (6.3)** and the ones **interested to keep using SENDER (6.4)** solutions after the demonstration ends.

KPI	INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	PARTNER	UNIT	SCALE	FREQUENCY
6.2	Perceived comfort/control/satisfaction	ECO	[1-5]	HH	Periodical
6.3	Share of users completing SENDER demonstration	ECO	[%]	PILOT	Demo end
6.4	N° of users interested to keep using SENDER	ECO	[%]	PILOT	Demo end

The relevance of KPIs proposed in this subchapter will strongly depend on the engagement strategies implemented in each pilot. At the time of writing, the pilots and responsible partners are

still discussing on the topic. The list of indicators will then be updated in Deliverable 7.1 “Report on number of consumers involved in the project”, which is due to M30 (March 2023).

3.3. Data analysis

This section describes the process foreseen for the data analysis to be made at the end of the pilot demonstration. The first step to assess the success of SENDER pilots is to define feasible targets for the KPIs defined in this deliverable. To do so, a brief benchmarking of DR campaigns and literature on demand-side flexibility is presented.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, SENDER aims to reach a **flexibility potential** from subscribed devices equal to **20%** of the households’ peak power and a **flexibility dispatchment** of **5 –10%** of the typical household energy consumption. These values are in line with reference literature and represent a realistic target for SENDER demonstration.

Indeed, model studies in “real life” smart grid environments reveal the ability of DR to reduce the demand peak between 3-6% (Staats et al., 2017) and 10-14% (Mazur & Goater, 2014). (Peacock & Owens, 2014) modelled a 35% maximum addressable opportunity of peak reduction, which falls to 12% using participation rates from actual field trials. (Kohlepp et al., 2019) reviewed DR field trials using thermal energy storage (HVAC & WHT) and found a potential of load shifting ranging between 10% and 48% of aggregate peak load, with the majority lying in the range 15–25% (for all type of control option and pricing scheme). Trials in the UK show that DR based on Time of Use (ToU) tariffs could reduce peak demand by up to 10% (Mazur & Goater, 2014). In China, an incentive-based DR campaign on 3.000 households resulted in average savings of 0.8 kWh per household during a 1.5h response period (Wang et al., 2020). In a Swedish field trial covering 136 households, price-based DR provoked a 4-17% mean reduction in electricity consumption (Nilsson et al., 2018).

No target has been set specifically for the increase of **self-consumption** from PV, nor for the reduction of **CO2 emissions** caused by SENDER.

In the analysis of (Staats et al., 2017), flexibility from wet appliances (dishwasher, washing machine) showed a median average peak reduction potential up to 35W, which results in an increase of PV self-consumption up to 129 kWh per household per year (6% of annual household demand).

SENDER aims to increase the profitability for consumers by decreasing **energy bills** of **5-10%**.

As a reference, the field test AEP Ohio GridSmart found moderate savings of around 5% in household and in wholesale electricity costs (Kohlepp et al., 2019). The simulations performed by the InteGRIDy project revealed a mean daily profit of 1.5%, which sets the theoretical maximum that can be extracted by a small portfolio of only four shiftable appliances (Bintoudi et al., 2021).

In terms of user participation, SENDER aims to reach 400 households for the demonstration and to increase profitability for DSOs by increasing by 20% the potential DR clients. Moreover, the project aims to maintain the **long-term engagement** of at least **50%** of consumers during the demonstration, which is seen as an ambitious target. The automation of SENDER solution aims at keeping the amount of **overrides** as small as possible, still **no target** of acceptance has been defined.

An average override rate of 12,9% through thermostat setpoint resetting has been recorded during the eco+ campaign launched by Ecobee in Canada (Sarran et al., 2021), where the effects of a big share of overrides (27%) caused the loss of up to 27.4% of the ideal power savings.

Table 4: List of benchmark and target values associated with each KPI defined in D7.2

KPI	PARTICIPATION IN SENDER DEMONSTRATION	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
0.1	Number of households enrolled in SENDER	[n°]	-	400
0.2	Flexibility potential available from controllable devices	[kW - %]	-	20%
KPI	UC1. EXPLICIT DEMAND RESPONSE	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
1.1	Flexibility dispatched - Total and share of load	[kWh - %]	>20 kWh	5 - 10%
1.1.EV	Flexibility dispatched from EV (up/down)	[kWh - %]	-	-
1.1.HVAC	Flexibility dispatched from HVAC (up/down)	[kWh - %]	15 - 25%	-
1.1.WHT	Flexibility dispatched from WHT (up/down)	[kWh - %]	15 - 25%	-
1.2	Load balance – Total and share of flexibility dispatched	[kWh - %]	-	-
1.3	Peak-to-Average load ratio – Forecasted and monitored	[%]	-35%	-
1.4	Profitability of explicit demand response for user	[€]	1,5 - 5%	5 - 10%
1.5	Emissions saved through flexibility dispatchment	[kg CO2]	-	-
1.6	Share of successful activations of flexible devices	[%]	87%	-
1.7	Share of time in flexible comfort range	[%]	-	-
KPI	UC2. MAXIMIZE SELF-CONSUMPTION	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
2.1	Avoided surplus electricity production sold to grid	[kWh]	-	-
2.2	Increase in share of self-consumption with SENDER	[%]	+6%	-
2.3	Electricity bills savings from self-consumption	[€]	-	5 - 10%
2.4	CO2 emissions savings from self-consumption	[kg CO2]	-	-
KPI	UC3. MINIMIZE ELECTRICITY BILLS	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
3.1	Electricity bills savings from price optimization	[€]	4 - 17%	5 - 10%
3.2	Price reduction of electricity purchased with SENDER	[€/kWh]	-5%	-
3.3	CO2 emissions savings from price optimization	[kg CO2]	-	-
KPI	UC5. PEER-TO-PEER TRADING	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
5.1	Average number of successful bids in P2P platform	[n°/d]	-	-
5.2	Increased share of PV production used onsite	[%]	-	-
5.3	Increased profit/savings from P2P trading	[€]	-	-
5.4	CO2 emissions saved from increased use of PV	[kg CO2]	-	-
KPI	INDICATORS OF ENGAGEMENT	UNIT	BENCHMARK	TARGET
6.1	Number of people reached/engaged/registered	[n°]	-	-
6.1.TG	N° or people engaged per target group	[n°]	-	-
6.2	Perceived comfort/control/satisfaction	[1-5]	-	-
6.3	Share of users completing SENDER demonstration	[%]	-	50%
6.4	N° of users interested to keep using SENDER	[%]	-	-

3.4. Differences between pilots

After presenting the KPIs that will serve to evaluate the effectiveness of SENDER, it is important to point out that each pilot have its particularities and that there will be some differences that will make unable the comparison of some aspects between pilots. The main ones are listed below:

- In Alginet (Spain), there will be **no aggregator involved** in the project, as there are none in Spain yet. This implies the testing of **UC1 as a simulation** carried out by the project partners, which will be tested without considering the grid needs or receiving signals from the grid to trigger the flexibility.

- For the other two pilots, in Austria and Finland, there will be a **signed contract with an aggregator**, who is interested in providing this demand flexibility service to the grid (DSO). There might be some differences between the two, in terms of the contract and the conditions or incentives agreed to be given to the participants.

- Regarding the pilot in Finland, it is expected to have a relatively **larger number of electric vehicles** compared with the other two. This might not only be a difference in the sample data, but to the extent of considering specific KPIs for this pilot.

- Finland will distribute its pilot in **two different locations**. This might create not only a difference between pilots, but also differences in results between the two locations from the same pilot.

- At the time this deliverable is written, Weiz (Austria) and VTT (Finland) are checking the possibility of developing UC5, which would consider **peer-to-peer trading** of energy among participants. In both cases, P2P could only be applied within members of an energy community, which is legally entitled to exchange electricity internally.

- Finally, it is expected to have differences regarding the **type of energy tariff** that the households will have, which might influence the impact potential of UC3. In Spain and Finland households can adopt a ToU tariff, which consists in different electricity prices depending on the hour of the day, whereas in Austria only fixed electricity tariffs are available, which limits the adaptation of demand to lower prices and therefore reduces the energy bill.

3.5. Limitations

This section is meant to outline the limitations which could affect the development of SENDER project as expected or may affect directly or indirectly the results. The main concerns are:

Risk of missing data – This might occur in different possible ways: firstly, if for some reason some SENDER boxes become disconnected or experience a failure, some data might get lost until the unit is restored. This can affect the whole sample if it occurs frequently. On the hand, some KPIs require the acquisition of external data, coming from the electricity market for example, and it might be difficult to gather all data as expected. An example could be having a dynamic CO2 emission factor for the electricity mix, instead of having a fixed one. To demonstrate the feasibility of UC1 to be extended broadly in future energy markets, it is crucial to have a CO2 emission factor every hour, as the flexibility demand acts according to the renewable production when possible.

Risk of having too little devices to implement UC2 and UC3 – UC2 is directly related with Evs and HWTs that use electricity as an energy source. Therefore, if a household has a PV system, but neither of those devices, UC2 cannot be implemented. Also, it is expected that a large part of the sample may not have renewable technologies installed, which reduces the chances of testing UC2 and obtain valuable results, reducing the impact of SENDER demonstration. A similar situation happens with UC3: if the main energy consumption is done by devices running gas or other energy sources than electricity, the possibility of implementing UC3 drastically reduces.

Differences between energy tariffs – Some households might have a ToU tariff, while others might have a fixed price for electricity. The latter ones will find it impossible to implement UC3 as shifting the demand would not imply an economic impact in their bills.

Lack of interest from aggregators – It could be difficult to find an aggregator interested in participating in the pilots because of a too small amount of flexibility offered by households or a

dissonance between the aggregator business model and the capabilities offered by SENDER requirements; an aggregator, for example, could be interested in participating only if it is able to control the forecasting, a condition which cannot be conceded by SENDER.

Difficult to compare real cases vs simulated ones (UC1) – Without an aggregator, the number of activations of devices during the simulation will not provide any value as an indicator. Similarly, users could still override a simulated DR action, but this operation does not assume the same importance as for a real case where flexibility requested from an aggregator cannot be provided due to an override. Also, different incentives will be proposed to those signing a contract with an aggregator and those who participate to a simulation. Finally, it could happen that the simulated DR actions happen with a different frequency, higher or lower, than for real cases.

Potential impact of inefficient behaviour – If users develop inefficient or inappropriate behaviour, like disconnecting devices or opening the windows all day, it will be difficult to reach a demand reduction when comparing the actual consumption with the baseline previous to the demonstration.

Difficulty of detecting UCs if implemented simultaneously – If a household is suitable for several UCs, there might be situations where two or more UCs overlap, generating doubts on which has been responsible for the flexibility provided. For example, increasing the demand during low-tariff moment (UC3) when at the same time PV panels are producing (UC2).

4. Conclusions

The demonstration of SENDER solutions undertaken in WP7 can provide valuable insights on the potential of residential Demand Response in different European countries. This Deliverable defined common data requirements for the three solutions providers of SENDER project, in order to allow the calculation of relevant KPIs for the analysis of the demonstration results.

The KPIs were categorized based on the Use Cases previously defined by the project Consortium, enabling to extrapolate the results of separate UCs to the national level of pilot sites. Most KPIs will be calculated at household level, making use of the detailed granularity of both the monitoring and the forecasting components implemented.

The flexibility dispatchment (1.1), the load balance (1.2) and the Peak-to-Average load ratio (1.3) will assess the extent to which households can offer flexibility to the electricity market. The economic benefits of the different UCs will be assessed in terms of profitability of DR (1.4 and 5.3), electricity bills savings (2.3, 3.1 and 5.3) and price reduction (3.2). The environmental benefits will be expressed as avoided PV surplus sold (2.1), increased share of self-consumption (2.2 and 5.2) and CO₂ emissions savings (1.5, 2.4, 3.3 and 5.4).

Additional KPIs will quantify the amount of households participating (0.1), the flexibility potential available (0.2) and the engagement of end-users before (6.1), during (6.2) and after the demonstration (6.3 and 6.4). Finally, some KPIs will assess the success of technical solutions (1.6), their rate of use (5.1) or the discomfort burden sustained by users (1.7).

The exact calculation procedure of the KPIs will depend on the specific constraints and adaptations encountered at each pilot site during the preparatory phases previous to the demonstration, including the engagement of users and the installation of SENDER components. The definition of KPIs will be then revised at the beginning of the pilots' demonstration, under the workload of Task 7.5 "Analysis of results".

A. Annexes

1.1. Registration and consent form

In the recruitment phase prior to developing the pilot, a registration form will be used to gather some information about the household and building characteristics of the families interested in participating in the project. This questionnaire should be completed by new participants and includes information needed to carry out the installation and the procurement of hardware conveniently.

The questionnaire can be completed both in paper and online, depending on the type of recruitment situation, which could be in a public event, a fair, a webinar or similar.

REGISTRATION FORM

PART 1: PERSONAL INFORMATION OF THE PARTICIPANT

Name: _____ Surname: _____

Full Address (street, number, floor...): _____

Post Code, City, Country: _____

Phone number: _____ Email: _____

Gender:

Male	Female	Other
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Age:

18-24	25-34	35-50	51-65	+65
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Individual Income level (per month, before taxing):

	< 1.500 €	1.500 – 2.499 €	2.500 – 3.499 €	> 3.500 €	N/A
Austria	< 1.500 €	1.500 – 2.499 €	2.500 – 3.499 €	> 3.500 €	N/A
Finland	< 1.500 €	1.500 – 2.799 €	2.800 – 4.199 €	> 4.200 €	N/A
Spain	< 1.166 €	1.167 – 1.999 €	2.000 – 2.999 €	> 3.000 €	N/A

PART 2: INFORMATION ON THE DWELLING

Nº of people living at home:

	0	1	2	3	4	5
Number of Women	0	1	2	3	4	5
Number of Men	0	1	2	3	4	5
Number of Others	0	1	2	3	4	5

Nº of people per Age ranges:

	0	1	2	3	4	5
0 - 7	0	1	2	3	4	5
8 - 17	0	1	2	3	4	5
18 - 24	0	1	2	3	4	5
25 - 34	0	1	2	3	4	5
35 - 50	0	1	2	3	4	5
51 - 65	0	1	2	3	4	5
+ 65	0	1	2	3	4	5

Housing characteristics:

Type of dwelling	Detached	Semi-detached	Multi-family house	Apartment
Tenure arrangement	Rent		Own	

Annex 1.1: Template of the first page of SENDER registration form, in english

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